

The Influence of Technology Acceptance Model on Intention to Use Electronic Government Systems with Trust as a Mediation Variable (Study of the General Election Commission Secretariat State Civil Apparatus in Lampung Province)

Yuanita Christianti¹, RR Erlina², Keumala Hayati³

^{1,2,3} Master of Management Program, Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Lampung, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

Published Online: June 11, 2024

The General Election Commission is a national, permanent and independent election organizing institution which is tasked with carrying out elections and has working areas throughout the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. The problem that occurs in the research object is that the Technology Acceptance Model and electronic-based government systems create a gap for employees with various conditions of ability to use technology that continues to develop. The aim of this research is to determine the influence of the Technology Acceptance Model on the intention to use an electronic-based government system with trust as a mediating variable in the state civil apparatus of the General Election Commission Secretariat in Lampung Province.

This research is quantitative research and was analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis. The data used in this research was obtained from the results of questionnaire testing on 251 employees from the State Civil Apparatus Secretariat of the General Election Commission in Lampung Province who were sampled in the research using the Stratified random sampling technique. The results obtained from this research are that Perceived Ease of Us (PeoU) has a positive and significant effect on the intention to use SPBE, Perceived Usefulness (PU) has a positive and significant effect on the intention to use SPBE, Perceived Ease of Us (PeoU) has a positive and significant effect on trust in SPBE, Perceived Usefulness (PU) has a positive and significant effect on trust in SPBE, Trust in SPBE has a negative and insignificant effect on intention to use SPBE, Trust in SPBE is unable to mediate the influence of Perceived Ease of Us (PeoU) on intention to use SPBE and Trust in SPBE is not able to mediate the influence of Perceived Usefulness (PU) on intention to use SPBE.

KEYWORDS:

Technology
Acceptance Model,
Electronic Based
Government System,
and Trust.

1. INTRODUCTION

The General Election Commission (KPU) is a national, permanent and independent election organizing institution which is tasked with carrying out elections and has a working area throughout the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. The KPU carries out its duties

continuously (<https://kpu.go.id>) The KPU is domiciled in the capital of the Republic of Indonesia, the Provincial KPU is domiciled in the provincial capital, and the Regency/City KPU is domiciled in the Regency/City capital.

The KPU is an extension of the Government which is required to be able to adapt to technological developments and adopt the use of this technology as part of the services that must be provided to all stakeholders as well as an effort to improve the quality of holding elections that are effective and efficient, transparent, accountable and accessible. For this reason, a system is needed that can optimize the use of advances in information technology in organizing elections.

The use of technology that supports government operations and governance is also one of the considerations in creating a system. Ease of use of technology is one thing that

Corresponding Author: Yuanita Christianti

**Cite this Article: Yuanita Christianti, RR Erlina, Keumala Hayati (2024). The Influence of Technology Acceptance Model on Intention to Use Electronic Government Systems with Trust as a Mediation Variable (Study of the General Election Commission Secretariat State Civil Apparatus in Lampung Province). International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies, 4(6), 493-499*

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needs to be considered because ultimately the use of a technology-based government system should provide convenience for anyone who accesses it, both the public and stakeholders, as well as KPU employees themselves who are tasked with providing adequate, transparent information and services. and accessible

The Technology of Acceptance Model (TAM) is an adaptation of a theory that studies Behavioral Intention where in this theory there are 2 (two) main variables which are the starting point for discussion, namely perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. Several studies show that TAM can be used as a dependent variable (Gu, Lee and Suh, 2009).

The role of trust in the use of e-government is an important factor that needs to be considered apart from the two factors above. It is very important to explore the role of trust because low trust held by service users will hinder e-government enforcement. (Kumar et al., 2007) Trust can influence the use of e-government. (Bélanger and Carter, 2008).

Several literatures have identified factors that influence the implementation of e-government, both from the government's perspective and from the community's perspective. TAM is primarily used to identify and study society's underlying motivations for adopting new technologies (Lean et al., 2009). TAM focuses more on psychological discussions of users rather than aspects of technology or devices used (Veeramootoo, Nunkoo and Dwivedi, 2018). TAM defines Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use as the main factors influencing technology adoption (Lallmahomed, Lallmahomed and Lallmahomed, 2017).

Kepercayaan adalah penentu penting adopsi Trust is an important determinant of internet technology adoption (Lean et al., 2009). On the other hand, to determine the administration of e-government achievements, it is mandatory to consider trust factors (Lallmahomed, Lallmahomed and Lallmahomed, 2017). Previous studies have proven that trust influences behavioral intentions to use technology (Kurfalı et al., 2017).

E-government services are defined as the use of information technology to improve the quality and delivery of services related to the public and government, so that the use of e-government services is considered capable of benefiting the government and its citizens (Kurfalı et al., 2017). One of the important goals of implementing e-government is to improve the performance of government services. (Bélanger and Carter, 2008). With the massive development of technology, accompanied by comfortable and easily accessible services, it will make it easier for the government to focus on providing good quality services for the community (Lean et al., 2009).

E-government services have strong potential in improving the quality of government systems in any country,

including Indonesia. Studies show that e-government has the potential to transform government itself, thereby improving the quality of services and increasing trust among citizens (Sang, Lee and Lee, 2009). E-government was also found to be more cost-effective and more convenient to use. Although the initial investment to build e-government seems large, the returns are profitable in the long term (Verkijika and Wet, 2018).

From the KPU of the Republic of Indonesia Documentation and Legal Information Network page, General Election Commission Regulation Number 5 of 2021 concerning the Implementation of the General Election Commission's Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE). Electronic Based Government System, hereinafter abbreviated as SPBE, is a government administration that utilizes information and communication technology to provide services to SPBE Users.

General Election Commission Regulation Number 5 concerning the Implementation of SPBE is intended as a guideline for all employees and work units in implementing SPBE at the KPU, Provincial KPU and Regency/City KPU in terms of increasing the integration and efficiency of electronic-based government systems and as an embodiment of clean government governance. , effective, transparent and accountable and providing quality and trustworthy public services at the KPU, Provincial KPU and Regency/City KPU.

One application of SPBE in the KPU is the use of the SIPOL (Political Party Information System) application which is used to present information related to data on political parties participating in the election. In the previous election, political parties who participated in the election traditionally registered with the KPU by bringing a number of physical documents which had to be verified by the KPU. This document consists of information containing the management list, membership list and legality of political parties from the central management level to the regional level management.

In the 2024 Election, SIPOL is used as a tool to verify administrative data from political parties participating in the Election. The KPU only checks data uploaded by management at the central level and if errors or deficiencies in data occur, the political parties participating in the election will be given time to correct them. Data in SIPOL can have limited access by Bawaslu, political parties participating in the election, and the general public. This illustrates that the stages of registering political parties as election participant candidates have been carried out in a transparent, accessible, accountable, and effective and efficient manner.

Another impact of implementing a digital office administration system is the emergence of a gap between employees within the Lampung Province KPU itself. Of the total 547 employees in Lampung Province, the number of civil servants is 260 people and PPNPN is 287 people.

For employees with a higher level of education and who

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are in the productive age range, technological developments do not become an obstacle in carrying out their duties and functions at work. However, this is not the case with employees who are older in age range, the application of technology which is expected to make it easier to carry out tasks in the workplace actually becomes counterproductive due to the lack of mastery of technological devices and technology-based work systems. In the end, this becomes an obstacle to the process of employee involvement in the work they carry out.

This is a phenomenon worthy of research considering that the impact of technology has become something that cannot be separated from the daily lives of today's society, especially in a government organization whose development is very dynamic and demands openness in presenting data and providing complete services to the public. For this reason, this research was prepared as a form of responsibility which is expected to provide contributions and possible corrective steps to be implemented to improve the Lampung Province KPU institution in the future.

The problems raised in this thesis are too broad to be examined thoroughly. Therefore, the researcher limits the discussion in this research and focuses his research on factors from the TAM Theory that influence the intentions of General Election Commission employees in Lampung Province in using the Electronic-Based Government System developed by the General Election Commission and used in the 2024 General Election Stages.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Electronic Based Government System (SPBE)

E-Government is an important tool for the government in meeting the growing needs of society (Napitupulu, 2017). This development is based on the existence of a cycle of change in the bureaucratic environment which has moved into the domain of the globalization environment (Sianggaran, 2020). So public policies are needed to implement automation in the government sector.

Technology Acceptance Model Technology Acceptance Model / TAM

Technology is one of the driving factors for change that occurs in an organization. Based on OEDC (2018) quoted from (Al Yami and Ajmal, 2019). Trust, reliability, accountability, innovation and quality of public sector services are the keys to increasing the will of society, business and other stakeholders. Thus, building public trust is an important goal that must be developed from an early age by stakeholders in organizations operating in the public sector (Horst, Kuttschreuter and Gutteling, 2007).

Trust

Trust is an important determinant of internet technology adoption (Abu - Shanab EA, 2017). On the other hand, to

determine the administration of e-government achievements, it is mandatory to consider trust factors (Zhao F, 2013). Previous studies have proven that trust influences behavioral intentions to use technology (Gu JC and Suh YH, 2009).

Hipotesis

H1: Perceived Ease of Use (PeoU) has a positive and significant effect on intention to use SPBE.

H2: Perceived Usefulness (PU) has a positive and significant effect on intention to use SPBE.

H3: Perceived Ease of Use (PeoU) has a positive and significant effect on trust in SPBE.

H4: Perceived Usefulness (PU) has a positive and significant effect on trust in SPBE

H5: Trust in SPBE has a positive and significant effect on intention to use SPBE

H6: Trust in SPBE mediates the influence of Perceived Ease of Use (PeoU) on intention to use SPBE

H7: Trust in SPBE mediates the influence of Perceived Usefulness (PU) on intention to use SPBE

III. RESEARCH METHOD

The objects of this research are the State Civil Apparatus who work within the Secretariat of the General Election Commission throughout Lampung Province. The Lampung Provincial General Election Commission Secretariat is a work unit that oversees 15 Regency/City General Election Commission Secretariats in Lampung Province.

This research directs the object of research to the State Civil Apparatus, both those with PNS status and those with PPNPN status who serve in the General Election Commission Secretariat in Lampung Province which is spread across 1 (one) work unit at the Provincial level and 15 (fifteen) work units at the Regency/Regency level. City. The total population of civil servants and PPNPN is 547 people.

This research uses the method from Roscoe (1975) in Sekaran, Uma (2003) to determine the number of research samples, namely using a sample size greater than 30 and less than 500 samples. Based on the theory above, the number of samples in this study was 251 ASN spread under the scope of the General Election Commission Secretariat in Lampung Province.

The data analysis method used in this research is using SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) with the help of the AMOS 24 application. This research uses a questionnaire to collect primary data. Primary data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires using a Google Form link via WhatsApp which could be accessed by respondents. Primary data will then be processed to provide coding to make it easier to tabulate respondents' answers.

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IV. RESULT

This research model consists of four constructs, namely Perceived ease of use (X1), Perceived Usefulness (X2), E government (M), and Intention to use (Y). Evaluation of a measurement model is a stage for testing the validity and reliability of a construct.

The model validity test is carried out to determine whether the indicators are valid or not in measuring variables. This is done by calculating convergent validity and discriminant validity. Convergent validity can be seen through outer loading and discriminant validity is calculated using the AVE root value. An instrument can be said to be valid if it meets the convergent validity test if it has an outer loading > 0.5 and an AVE value > 0.5.

The results of the measurement analysis show that all indicators measuring the variables Perceived ease of use (X1), Perceived Usefulness (X2), E Government (M), and Intention to Use (Y) have loading factor values and AVE values greater than 0.5. In this way, the indicator is declared valid for measuring the variable

Construct reliability testing was carried out using the Cronbach's Alpha technique. The test criteria state that if the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is ≥ 0.6 , it means that the construct can be said to be reliable or a consistent indicator in measuring the variables it measures. The summary of reliability testing results is as follows:

Table 1. Reliability Test

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	CR	Cut Off	Inf
X1	0.982	0.977	0.6	Reliable
X2	0.971	0.965	0.6	Reliable
M	0.920	0.887	0.6	Reliable
Y	0.950	0.930	0.6	Reliable

Source: Processed data, 2024

Table 1 shows that the Cronbach's Alpha value for the variables Perceived ease of use (X1), Perceived Usefulness (X2), E government (M), and Intention to Use (Y) is greater than 0.6. Thus, based on Cronbach's Alpha calculations, all indicators measuring the variables Perceived ease of use (X1), Perceived Usefulness (X2), E government (M), and Intention to Use (Y) are declared reliable.

Construct Feasibility Test (Model)

Testing the suitability of the construct (model) is intended to determine whether the construct formed is appropriate (feasible) or not. There are several test indices in SEM analysis, namely Chi Square (CMIN)/df, RMR, RMSEA, GFI, AGFI, TLI, CFI, RFI, and NFI. The results of the model feasibility testing are summarized in the following table:

Tabel 2. Goodnes Of Fit

Indeks	Goodnes Of Fit	Cut Off Value	Inf
Chi-Square (CMIN) / df	2.772	≤ 5	Good fit
GFI	0.916	≥ 0.9	Good fit
RMR	0.50	≤ 0.5	Good fit
RMSEA	0.08	≤ 0.08	Good fit
TLI	0.910	≥ 0.9	Good fit
NFI	0.923	≥ 0.9	Good fit
AGFI	0.902	≥ 0.9	Good fit
RFI	0.912	≥ 0.9	Good fit
CFI	0.917	≥ 0.9	Good fit

Source: Processed data, 2024

Based on the goodness of fit summary, it can be seen that of the 9 (nine) indices, it is known that all the CMIN / df, GFI, RFI, AGFI, RMR, RMSEA, TLI, NFI, and CFI indices state that the model is good fit. It was concluded that the SEM path diagram that had been formed was suitable for use in this research.

Hypothesis testing

Direct effect and indirect effect hypothesis testing is intended to test whether there is an influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. Significance testing can be determined through probability values. The test criteria state that if the p value < level of significance (alpha ($\alpha=5\%$)) then it is stated that there is a significant influence of the exogenous variable on the endogenous variable. The results of the analysis can be seen through the summary in the following table:

Table 3. Hypothesis testing

Hipotesis	Path	Estimate	SE	p value	Inf.
H1	$X1 \rightarrow Y$	0.557	0.142	0.000	Positive, significant
H2	$X2 \rightarrow Y$	0.747	0.130	0.000	Positive, significant
H3	$X1 \rightarrow M$	0.481	0.095	0.000	Positive, significant
H4	$X2 \rightarrow M$	0.541	0.094	0.000	Positive, significant
H5	$M \rightarrow Y$	-0.270	0.193	0.163	Negative, insignificant
H6	$X1 \rightarrow M \rightarrow Y$	-0.173	0.413	0.197	Negative, insignificant
H7	$X2 \rightarrow M \rightarrow Y$	-0.201	0.497	0.133	Negative, insignificant

Source: Processed data, 2024

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Based on the table above, it can be seen that the mathematical model is formed:

$$\text{Equation 1: } M = 0.481 X1 + 0.541 X2$$

$$\text{Equation 2: } Y = 0.557 X1 + 0.747 X2 - 0.270 M$$

Discussion

The influence of Perceived Ease of Use (PeoU) on intention to use SPBE

Testing the influence of Perceived ease of use (X1) on Intention to Use (Y) produces a p value of <0.001. The test results show that the p value (0.000) < level of significance (alpha = 5%). This means that at a real level of 5% it can be stated that there is a significant influence of Perceived ease of use on Intention to Use. The path coefficient for Perceived ease of use is 0.557, indicating that Perceived ease of use has a positive effect on Intention to Use. This means that the higher the perceived ease of use, the more likely it is to increase the Intention to Use. In accordance with hypothesis 1 (H1) in this study, namely Perceived Ease of Use (PeoU) has a positive and significant effect on intention to use SPBE, it is supported.

The influence of Perceived Usefulness (PU) on intention to use SPBE

Testing the influence of Perceived Usefulness (X2) on Intention to Use (Y) produces a p value of <0.001. The test results show that the p value (0.000) < level of significance (alpha = 5%). This means that at a real level of 5% it can be stated that there is a significant influence of Perceived Usefulness on Intention to Use. The path coefficient for Perceived Usefulness is 0.747, indicating that Perceived Usefulness has a positive effect on Intention to Use. This means that the higher the Perceived Usefulness, the greater the Intention to Use. In accordance with hypothesis 2 (H2) in this research, namely Perceived Usefulness (PU) has a positive and significant effect on intention to use SPBE, it is supported.

The influence of Perceived Ease of Use (PeoU) on trust in SPBE

Testing the influence of Perceived ease of use (X1) on E Government (M) produces a p value of <0.001. The test results show that the p value (0.000) < level of significance (alpha = 5%). This means that at a real level of 5% it can be stated that there is a significant influence of Perceived ease of use on E Government. The path coefficient for Perceived ease of use is 0.481, indicating that Perceived ease of use has a positive effect on E Government. This means that the higher the perceived ease of use, the more likely it is to increase E Government. In accordance with hypothesis 3 (H3) in this research, namely Perceived Ease of Use (PeoU) has a positive and significant effect on SPBE trust.

The influence of Perceived Usefulness (PU) on SPBE trust

Testing the effect of Perceived Delight (X2) on E Government (M) produces a p value of <0.001. Test result shows that the p value (0.000) > level of significance (alpha

= 5%). This means that at a real level of 5% it can be stated that there is a significant influence of Perceived Usefulness on E Government. The path coefficient for Perceived Usefulness is 0.541, indicating that Perceived Usefulness has a positive effect on E Government. This means that the higher the Perceived Usefulness, the more likely it is to increase E Government. In accordance with hypothesis 4 (H4) in this research, namely that Perceived Usefulness (PU) has a positive and significant effect on SPBE trust, it is supported.

The influence of trust in SPBE on intention to use SPBE

Testing the influence of E Government (M) on Intention to Use (Y) produces a p value of 0.163. The test results show that the p value (0.163) > level of significance (alpha = 5%). This means that at a real level of 5% it can be stated that there is no significant influence of E Government on Intention to Use. The path coefficient for E Government is -0.270, indicating that E Government has a negative effect on Intention to Use. The research results show that E-Government has a negative and insignificant effect on Intention to Use. This means that trust in SPBE does not influence the intentions of General Election Commission employees in using SPBE. In accordance with hypothesis 5 (H5) in this study, namely that trust in SPBE has a positive and significant effect on intention to use SPBE, it is not supported.

Trust in SPBE mediates the influence of Perceived Ease of Use (PeoU) on intention to use SPBE

Testing the influence of Perceived ease of use (X1) on Intention to Use (Y) through E Government (M) produces a p value of 0.197. The test results show that the p value (0.197) > level of significance (alpha = 5%). This means that at a real level of 5% it can be stated that there is no significant influence of Perceived ease of use on Intention to Use through E Government, or in other words that the E Government variable is unable to mediate the influence of Perceived ease of use on Intention to Use. It can be seen from the table that the coefficient has a negative value of - 0.173, which means that E Government is unable to positively mediate Perceived ease of use on Intention to Use. This means that trust in SPBE does not mediate the influence of Perceived Ease of Use (PeoU) on intention to use SPBE. This means that trust in SPBE as a mediating variable is not able to strengthen the influence of Perceived ease of use in increasing the intention of General Election Commission employees to use SPBE. In accordance with hypothesis 6 (H6) in this study, namely that trust in SPBE mediates the influence of Perceived Ease of Use (PeoU) on intention to use SPBE, it is not supported.

Trust in SPBE mediates the influence of Perceived Usefulness (PU) on intention to use SPBE

Testing the influence of Perceived Usefulness (X2) on Intention to Use (Y) through E Government (M) produces a p value of 0.133. The test results show that the p value (0.133) > level of significance (alpha = 5%). This means that at a real

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level of 5% it can be stated that there is no significant influence of Perceived Usefulness on Intention to Use through E Government, or in other words that the E Government variable is unable to mediate the influence of Perceived Usefulness on Intention to Use. It can be seen from the table that the coefficient has a negative value of -0.201, which means that E Government is unable to positively mediate Perceived Usefulness on Intention to Use. This means that trust in SPBE as a mediating variable is not able to strengthen the influence of Perceived Usefulness in increasing the intention of General Election Commission employees to use SPBE. In accordance with hypothesis 7 (H7) in this study, namely that trust in SPBE mediates the influence of Perceived Usefulness (PU) on intention to use SPBE, which is not supported.

V. CONCLUSION

This research examines the influence of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) on the intentions of General Election Commission employees to use Electronic-Based Government Systems in the 2024 General Election. The research results show that this research supports the proposed hypothesis (H1), namely that Perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on intentions to use SPBE. The research results show that this research supports the proposed hypothesis (H2), namely that Perceived Usefulness has a positive and significant effect on the intention to use SPBE. The research results show that this research supports the proposed hypothesis (H3), namely that Perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on E Government. The research results show that this research supports the proposed hypothesis (H4), namely that Perceived Usefulness has a positive and significant effect on E Government (M). The research results show that this research does not support the proposed hypothesis (H5), namely that trust in SPBE has a positive and significant effect on intention to use SPBE. The research results show that this research does not support the proposed hypothesis (H6), namely that trust in SPBE mediates the influence of Perceived Ease of Us (PeoU) on intention to use SPBE. The research results show that this research does not support the proposed hypothesis (H7), namely that trust in SPBE mediates the influence of Perceived Usefulness (PU) on intention to use SPBE. Because, the research results show that Perceived Usefulness has a negative and insignificant effect on Intention to Use via E-Government. Regarding the use of government systems in the long term, the KPU should develop a more attractive and informative information system so that it can become a trusted source in providing electoral information to its users. Future research can increase the sample size and study area coverage to achieve more precise results. Apart from that, further research can be done on the influence of other factors such as user comfort and innovation in developing KPU

electronic-based government systems.

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